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Abstract	<p>This report analyzes individual use cases for the STRATEGIC Project, focusing on digital health technologies (DHTs) in clinical research and trials. We selected seven use cases from Cameroon, Ghana, Mozambique, Kenya, and South Africa, examining the involved entities, implemented technologies, and their applications. The report details the selection process, qualitative research findings from interviews and site visits, and includes policy recommendations. Key insights highlight best practices for data security and patient protection in line with WHO protocols. Our findings stress that investing in DHTs is crucial for enhancing diagnostic efficiency, communication between clinicians and patients, and improving remote consultations and patient recruitment for trials.</p>
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Executive Summary

This report presents a detailed analysis of individual use cases for the STRATEGIC Project, along with a cross-analysis of those cases. These use cases involve projects or institutions that are using digital health technologies (DHTs) for clinical trials or clinical research. We provide insights into the entities involved, the technologies they are implementing, and how these technologies are being applied. We have selected and confirmed seven use cases, and this report outlines the selection process, the qualitative research conducted through interviews and discussion during site visits, key findings that underpin the analysis, and policy recommendations derived from these case studies. Use cases for the project were selected from five countries within sub-Saharan Africa; Cameroon, Ghana, Mozambique, Kenya and South Africa. The cases turned around epidemiological health systems management, data collection, clinical research and trials practices. With regards to findings, although each use case is unique, multiple insights were gleaned across the board like the conceptualization of best practices for data security and patient protection through the respect of World Health Organization (WHO) protocols and country implementation of governmental policies. Our findings also indicated that investment in DHTs is an imperative for nations involved as it enhances efficiency in diagnostics protocols, efficient communication systems between clinicians and patients as well as remote consultation and patient recruitment for clinical trials.

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Table I: List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
CIS	Cellule d'Information Sanitaire
DHIS2	District Health Information Software version 2
DHTs	Digital Health Technologies
EHRs	Electronic Health Records
EPI	Expanded Programme on Immunisation
FDG	Focus Group Discussion
GIZ	German Corporation for International Cooperation
GPS	Global Positioning System
KI	Key Informant
MARS	Mobile Application Rating Scale
NTDs	Neglected Tropical Diseases
ODK	Open Data Kit
ONER	ONE Record Server
SMS	Short Message Service
STRATEGIC	Sustainable ethics reviews of digital health technology design in sub-Saharan Africa
SSA	Sub-Saharan Africa
UNICEF	United Nations Children's Fund
WHO	World Health Organization

Table II: Glossary of terms

Term	Explanation
AI	Artificial intelligence (AI) is a set of technologies that enable computers to perform a variety of advanced functions, including the ability to see, understand and translate spoken and written language, analyze data, make recommendations, and more.
Digital Health Technology	Any health technologies used for clinical trials and research
DHIS2	Is a web-based software that allows for the compilation and analysis of health indicators at various levels, including district, regional, and national levels.
GenExpert	A molecular diagnostic platform that uses polymerase chain reaction to detect specific DNA or RNA sequences, enabling rapid and accurate diagnosis of various diseases.
ODK	An open-source mobile data collection platform. It enables users to fill out forms offline and send form data to a server when a connection is found
RedCap	A web application for building and managing online surveys and databases
ONER	The ONE Record Server (ONER) is a key component of the ONE Record initiative, serving as a central data hub for logistics information in the air cargo industry. It offers a standardized, web API-based interface that enables the sharing and access of shipment data. This ensures that all authorized parties have a single, consistent view of each shipment.

1. Introduction

Digital health technology leverages digital tools and information and communication technologies (ICT) to enhance healthcare delivery and improve patient outcomes. These encompass telemedicine, mobile health applications, electronic health records, wearable devices, artificial intelligence, and data analytics. These technologies are designed to overcome barriers in healthcare by providing secure access to health-related information and facilitating efficient data management. These technologies have the potential to transform healthcare through increased efficiency, personalized care, patient engagement, remote consultations, continuous monitoring, timely interventions, and advancements in medical research (Awad et al., 2021 ; Borges do Nascimento et al., 2023) Digital health technologies (DHTs) have emerged as powerful tools that can transform medical practices and research worldwide (Global Strategy on Digital Health 2020-2025). In Sub-Saharan Africa, where healthcare systems face numerous challenges, these technologies offer significant potential to bridge gaps, enhance healthcare delivery, and advance medical research. Several countries in the region have made progress in integrating technologies such as mHealth, Electronic Health Records (EHRs), telemedicine, cloud-based applications, and Artificial Intelligence (AI) into their healthcare systems, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic (Ibeneme et al., 2022; Manyazewal et al., 2021; Rinke de Wit et al., 2022).

Digital health technologies are playing a transformative role in healthcare across Africa, despite facing challenges and barriers to adoption. These innovations empower both clinicians and patients through solutions for remote monitoring, data collection, and ongoing tracking. However, ensuring information systems security requires a strong technological foundation. In low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), there is often a lack of national guidelines to support the implementation of digital security best practices (Lustig 2012; Data Science, 2019). Moreover, these technologies are advancing clinical research and improving access to quality healthcare throughout the world. Their applications are diverse and continue to evolve, leading to an array of use cases. The Sustainable Ethics Review of Digital Health Technology Design in Sub-Saharan Africa (STRATEGIC) project highlights the importance of involving various stakeholders—such as healthcare professionals, researchers, policymakers, and local communities—in the development and implementation of digital health technologies. By adopting a co-creation approach, the project seeks to tailor solutions to the specific cultural, social, and contextual nuances of SSA.

The STRATEGIC project considers use cases as a critical part of co-creating a responsible framework for the ethical evaluation of digital health technologies for clinical trials and research in Africa. The main justification for the pertinence of the study is contextual relevance of practical cases of use. Use cases provide concrete examples that reflect the real-world ethical and legal challenges, needs, and effectiveness of the use of technologies for clinical research in Africa. The assumption is that use cases will ensure the co-created framework addresses the diversity of health systems, regulatory environments, and socio-economic contexts across the continent. Use of cases or case studies also enables effective collaboration by providing a shared reference point for discussions among stakeholders, including researchers, clinicians, patients, regulators, and technology providers.

Additionally, context-specific use cases which we have selected here will help to highlight ethical dilemmas and cultural nuances that might otherwise be overlooked. The aim, therefore, is to calibrate the use cases that will demonstrate practical challenges and bottlenecks in the use of digital health technologies as well as help in identifying risks associated with technology misuse or unintended consequences in clinical trials in order to enhance efficiency. Finally, use cases across diverse settings ensure the framework can scale and adapt to various contexts in Africa, from urban to rural environments guaranteeing a globalised functional network across the continent.

In terms of key findings, some of the major insights from the case analysis included the common reality that DHTs facilitated communication and functionality in conflict zones and difficult to access rural areas. The effective recruitment of clinical trials participants using short message service (SMS) tools especially in the Northwest and Southwest conflict regions in Cameroon supported this standpoint.

2. Methodology and rationale for Use cases analysis

The goal of the use case analysis is to ensure that the development and implementation of Digital Health Technologies adhere to ethical standards, protect patient rights, and maintain quality and safety benchmarks. The objectives of the analysis included identifying seven specific use cases of DHTs for clinical research and clinical trials in five Sub-Saharan African countries. Confirming participation from research project coordinators for interviews, discussions, and/or site visits was crucial. These interactions gathered information from investigators, clinical research stakeholders and research program coordinators regarding the impact and opportunities of digital health technologies in clinical research in Sub-Saharan Africa.

2.1. Selection criteria:

To select the use cases, a set of inclusion and exclusion criteria was agreed by the consortium members. For a case to be included as part of the STRATEGIC use cases these criteria must be met:

- It must be a project or initiative being conducted in an institution in sub-Saharan Africa
- It must be using digital health technology – a document on what qualifies as DHT was developed.
- The project leaders ensured that participants agreed to be part of the use case interviews

2.2. Selection procedure:

We initially compiled a list of 12 projects using information from existing research networks, centres, and available online resources. After screening the projects, five were removed from consideration due to accessibility issues for interviews and limited information regarding their activities. Consequently, seven projects were selected, all of which confirmed their willingness to participate in the use case interviews and discussions. We defined the scope of the selection by cross-referencing our research

objectives with the contextual profiles of these seven projects. This process ensured that their inclusion aligned closely with the STRATEGIC project objectives.

2.3. Research milestone and insights:

This task is led by the University of Yaoundé 1 (LETS) in Cameroon. A comprehensive use case analysis protocol was developed, along with interview and discussion guides and informed consent documents, which were submitted to the Cameroon National Ethics Committee. The committee granted ethical clearance for the project. The interview protocol was pre-tested in pilot discussions and interviews with the Cameroon National Tuberculosis Programme, which uses the GenExpert digital system for diagnostics. Furthermore, use case interviews and site visits were conducted to gather qualitative data.

2.4. Research Approach and Analysis:

A qualitative research approach was employed for gathering relevant information, which included site visits, interviews, focus group discussions with researchers involved in clinical research projects utilizing Digital Health Technologies (DHTs) across five countries in Africa. All interviews were transcribed verbatim in original language, translated into English, and thematically coded. We conducted three rounds of coding, created the coding book and performed a thematic analysis as further described, to gather insights and develop policy recommendations. These recommendations will be essential for co-creating a responsible framework for the ethical evaluation of DHTs in clinical trials and research in Africa.

Participant selection

A purposive sampling technique was used to select participants for the study. This was done by contacting the directors of the research institutions that were identified as carrying out clinical research project utilizing DHT for analysis, data collection, patient observation, randomisation among others as explained above. On contact, participants were selected on recommendation to represent the institution by the institutional heads. These participants were selected experts who were directly involved with the design and implementation of the set clinical research project or programme. Figure 1 shows the study settings: Cameroon, Ghana, Kenya, Mozambique and South Africa. A total of five site visits, 15 interviews, and two focus group discussions were held across five African countries, as outlined in Table III. The interactions were carried out through face-to-face interviews, telephone interviews and round table discussions in English, French and Portuguese. These engagements provided valuable insights into the practical applications, benefits, and challenges associated with DHTs in Africa.

Data collection

Data collection was conducted in a closed and quiet room, away from the participants' work premises, to minimize disturbances and ensure high-quality audio recordings. A trained data collector led each interview session, accompanied by a note taker. Interviews were recorded using a Dictaphone.

Recordings from French and Portuguese interviews were subsequently transcribed and translated into English for analysis. Structured interviews were carried out using a pre-tested interview guide (Appendix 2) Interview sessions lasted from 20 minutes to an hour.

Thematic analysis

Data analysis was carried using thematic analysis. Categorical themes were formulated on initial literature review to identify questions that addressed in DHT implementation across SSA. These categories were: General Understanding, Implementation and Integration, Ethical issues, Data Management and Security, Stakeholder engagement, benefits and impact Future directions, Evaluation and measurement, Collaboration and partnerships related to DHT implementation. The analysis was conducted through the following steps:

Familiarization with the Data: All interviews were audio-recorded, transcribed verbatim, and reviewed for accuracy. Transcripts were read multiple times to gain an in-depth understanding of the content.

Generating Initial Codes: An inductive coding process was employed. Coding was performed manually to systematically organize meaningful data segments.

Reviewing Themes: The themes were refined through iterative comparison across transcripts, ensuring that each theme accurately represented the dataset and was distinct from others. Inconsistencies or overlaps were addressed through discussion among the research team.

Reporting: Final themes were supported by illustrative quotes from participants.

Data Management: All data were anonymized and stored securely. Transcripts were labelled using unique participant codes. Data management and coding were performed manually by three individual research assistants.

Figure 1: Map of site visits, interviews & discussion settings

Countries	Site visits	Interviews	Focus group discussion
Cameroon	3	6	1
Ghana	1	3	1
Kenya	/	1	/
Mozambique	/	2	/
South Africa	1	3	/
Total	5	15	2

Table III: Count of field visits, interviews, and discussions conducted in different countries

3. Use cases analysis: Results and discussion insights

3.1. Individual Use cases Analysis

Case 1: Digital Health Technology for Epidemiological Surveillance, health Information Systems, and Programme Management by the Ministry of Public Health in Cameroon

Case description and use of technology

The Ministry of Public Health in Cameroon has implemented a digital technology within its national health information system to enhance data collection, a data and storage. The District Health Information Software version 2 (DHIS2) programme uses digital technology for disease surveillance, health data management, and comprehensive data collection. DHIS2 serves as the primary platform for health data, enabling informed decision-making based on routine information. Additionally, the Ministry employs the Open Data Kit (ODK) for data collection, managed by the health information systems department called the Health Information Unit, known in French as ‘Système d’Information Sanitaire (CIS)’. ODK is an open-source platform that enables offline data collection via smartphones, making it particularly useful in remote or low-connectivity settings. Importantly, the Expanded Programme on Immunization (EPI) utilizes the DHIS2 framework to evaluate key vaccination performance indicators, such as data timeliness, accuracy, and completeness, under the data quality assessment framework implemented by the World Health Organisation.

Topic insights

Theme 1: Implementation and Integration of Digital Health Technologies

The participant a male public health specialist, described an extensive use of digital tools for vaccination and surveillance data management: *"We use software such as DHIS2, Excel, ERP, Power BI, and QGIS. For epidemiological surveillance, we also use Epi Info and ERH."*

Tools like ODK are used for field supervision, and YACO for integrating geospatial data for vaccination campaigns: *"We use ODK to collect data in the field, and the advantage is that you don't need an internet connection... YACO helps integrate data collection and geospatial analysis."*

Despite these efforts, integration into the national health information system is hampered by interoperability and governance challenges: *"We have challenges in terms of the interoperability of certain software... and a slightly bigger problem, which is governance."*

The EPI in Cameroon increasingly relies on digital tools to improve data collection and field supervision. ODK, was highlighted by a participant as a practical and effective solution for capturing real-time data during health interventions. ODK is an open-source platform that enables offline data collection via smartphones, making it particularly useful in remote or low-connectivity settings.

Its integration into supervisory activities is expected to improve the efficiency, accuracy, and timeliness of vaccination monitoring processes across the country. As one participant explained: *"There are still key components needed to ensure that vaccination efforts run smoothly across the country. One of these*

is supervision, which will support data collection using smartphones. For this, we plan to use ODK—Open Data Kit—technology. The advantage of ODK is that it allows data collection in the field without requiring an internet connection. So, for this aspect of supervision, ODK will be our primary tool."

Theme 2: Ethical Issues

The participant expressed concerns about the handling of confidential data:

Security and confidentiality remain a *"big concern today"*. The participant highlighted that epidemiological data are *"individual data,"* meaning they refer to specific persons and therefore *"must have a confidentiality agreement"* To mitigate risks, an intranet-based collaborative workspace was created: *"We set up an intranet based on Microsoft 365... people who have access are authorised users."* However, there's limited awareness of national data governance frameworks: *"Cameroon signed a presidential decree on personal data security... but I haven't looked through it yet."*

Theme 3: Benefits and Impact

The integration of digital technologies within the EPI has significantly enhanced data-driven decision-making and operational efficiency. The participant highlighted several key improvements. Participants identified improved data collection efficiency, enhanced data analysis, enabled real-time reporting, and standardized methods across regions among others as a benefit of using DHIS2. Using ODK enabled the collection of data without internet hence enabling data collection in areas with poor internet connection and areas without connectivity.

Enhanced Decision-Making: Digital tools have streamlined the data analysis process, allowing for quicker, evidence-based decisions: *"We can make decisions more quickly because we have the evidence... we now have unified databases."*

Improved Reporting Timeliness: The automation of routine tasks has accelerated the production of epidemiological reports, ensuring timely dissemination of information: *"Situation reports... come out more quickly because we've automated the tasks."*

Empowered Managers through Dashboards: Decision-makers now have access to real-time dashboards, reducing dependency on technical staff and enabling more autonomous responses to emerging issues: *"I can talk about situation reports, which is the epidemiological situation that we produce every week. They come out more quickly because we've automated the tasks using technology."*

As a result, our reports are quicker and faster.....we can find out the situation in any part of the country more quickly, without having to open Excel files to go through it all” (Male Participant, Data Manager, Ministry of Public Health, Cameroon). These advancements underscore the transformative potential of digital health technologies in strengthening public health systems and enabling data-informed leadership.

Theme 4: Stakeholder engagement

Although still limited, mechanisms for stakeholder engagement—particularly with patients—are in place within the surveillance component of the EPI system. The participant explained that patients are informed of their diagnostic results, especially in the context of epidemiological investigations: *“We tell [suspected cases] that the results were negative... if it's positive, we carry out in-depth investigations and keep them informed.”* This reflects a foundational level of feedback and communication with individuals whose data is being collected, marking an important step toward more participatory and transparent health data practices.

Theme 5: Evaluation and Measurement

The participant described key indicators used to assess the effectiveness of digital health technologies. These include both usage and impact metrics: *“The number of decisions taken using dashboards... the proportion of patients using mobile health technologies....”*

Such metrics reflect how technologies influence decision-making and patient engagement.

Beyond performance indicators, the participant emphasized the **qualitative improvement in data quality** as a result of technology adoption: *“If all these technologies are in place, the quality of the data will improve.”* This highlights the dual focus on measurable outcomes and systemic enhancements in health information accuracy and reliability.

Theme 6: Collaboration and Partnership

Cameroon's EPI collaborates with multiple partners in ensuring consistent financing and international support from host of organizations who have together contributed to ensuring a swift digitalization of

public health data in all pyramids of the health system. Some of these organizations have been listed in the following excerpts below: *"We work with the Ministry of Public Health's IT department, the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation, the Clinton Foundation, UNICEF, WHO, Blue Squad, and GIZ."*

These partnerships have tangible outcomes: *"With Blue Squad, we moved from Excel to large reusable databases for microplanning... WHO helped integrate ODK."* Each partner contributes based on assessed programmatic needs and were program key indicators need to be developed:

Theme 7: Challenges of implementing Digital Health Technology

In analysing the interview data, several themes were identified and categorised as challenges of implementing DHIS2. These themes included the operational cost of the digital tool, lack of trained personnel and limited access to the internet. The cost of acquiring new software, high internet cost and other information technologies required to use this software effectively was identified as a major challenge. A participant suggested the need for capacity building on the use of DHIS2 in order to leverage its capabilities in diseases surveillance: *"We have problems acquiring these tools—the software, the internet, and the people trained to use them. Capacity building is a big challenge; these tools can become too dependent on one person and need to be standardized so everyone can use them."*

Stakeholders also highlighted key systemic challenges within the national health information system (HIS). The use of different software by other national health control programs has led to difficulties in exchanging data between these programs. Also, the absence of proper coordination at the central level with regards to digital health technology adoption was identified as a key driver in its integration. This was discussed in the excerpt below: *"We have challenges in terms of the interoperability of certain software, so interoperability between what is used in the EPI and the CIS. So that remains a problem with the health information system. In fact, I think the big problem is interoperability and also a slightly bigger problem, which is governance. Because there are other software that we've decided to use, without the opinion of the health information system, which poses governance problems. We've solved the problem, but now it has to be integrated into the overall health information system. So, in terms of the health information system, we have the problem of governance and interoperability"*

Theme 8: Security and confidentiality issues

Data security and confidentiality were a common category of issues related to the use case. The respondent highlights challenges and solutions related to data security and confidentiality in the use of digital health technologies. With personal data not considered a security priority as compared to health data, data security remains a pertinent issue for health programs. This is reflected in the excerpt that follows: *“So, there are confidentiality issues. And in terms of security, it's true that in Africa we don't have data that's as hypersensitive as funding. But to solve part of this problem, we've set up an intranet for the Expanded Programme on Immunization, based on Microsoft 365. This means that we have a collaborative workspace, where the people who have access are people from the programme or people authorized to have access. This reinforces security a bit, and it also reinforces data confidentiality. So we're going to have compartments.”*

Theme 9: Future Perspectives

Looking forward, the key concern reported was managing the upcoming complexity from increased data volume and system diversity: *“In the future, we'll have major concerns with interoperability... more hospitals will develop systems with patient files”*. The participant recommended urgent deployment of a national digital health architecture by key stakeholders: *“We would like the digital health architecture to be set up quickly... we're working on a master facility list.”* Furthermore, DHIS2 is currently working on a programme that has been configured into the wider healthcare system and is funded by the main partner of the government, the Global Fund. Other partners include UNICEF that helps with the configuration and implementation as well as the training of administrators and users. There is constant retraining when updates are made.

Case 2: Digitalization of clinical research at the Higher Institute of Scientific and Medical Research (ISM, Cameroon)

Case description and use of technology

The Higher Institute of Scientific and Medical Research (ISM) is a not-for-profit organization created in 2005, located in Yaoundé, Cameroon. ISM aims to bring solutions to population health problems through fundamental and applied scientific research. ISM main missions are to (i) contribute to drug development, especially pre-clinical trials and phase I, II, and III clinical trials, (ii) assist the Ministry of Public Health through the development of a surveillance system for the monitoring, prevention and early management of serious adverse events occurring post-mass treatment campaigns with ivermectin, (iii)

conduct impact assessment with Ministry of Public Health major programmes, (iv) conduct basic and operational research activities for optimal control of infectious and non-communicable diseases, (v) provide student and young researchers with advanced training in biomedical research.

More specifically, ISM has long standing experience in clinical research, especially clinical trials (ISM has a Clinical Trial Centre and currently offering the facility to support phase I clinical trials) and observational studies (cross-sectional surveys, cohort studies or case-control studies and more). Patients/participants recruitment and randomization has been improved over years, from paper forms to electronic forms deployed on tablets and phones for real time data collection that enable a better follow-up of enrolment. The tools ISM uses for this real time surveys are ODK Collect, Kobo Collect or REDCaP. The implementation of DHTs in clinical research at ISM to enhance research outcomes was discussed in the sections below during interview sessions with two key implementers of digital lead projects at the institution. This interaction was followed by a focus group discussion with six participants, including the moderator and a note-taker.

Topic insights

Theme 1: Implementation and Integration of Digital Health Technology

One of the key digital health tools implemented by ISM in the WHO Skin NTD mobile application, which is designed to support health personnel in recognizing skin-related symptoms of neglected tropical diseases (NTDs). The participant was actively involved in the app's design, implementation, and evaluation.

“My role is to implement and evaluate the application... I work on the design, development of the technology, its implementation and its evaluation with different evaluation methods.”

Integration was achieved through collaboration with national and regional health authorities, in-person sensitization and WhatsApp-based training sessions for health workers, leveraging existing case-finding programs to embed the tool into healthcare workflows: *“We met the disease control directorate, regional delegations... so that the message gets through to the end of the chain that is the health personnel.”*

Theme 2: Ethical Issues

Although the current version of the application does not collect personal or patient data — minimizing privacy risks — the project still underwent ethical review: *“This application does not collect information on the patient, so there is no breach in terms of privacy or data security.”*

Ethical clearance to ensure the research project is in line with research ethics and national principles were obtained from the Cameroon National Ethics Committee of Research for Human Health and regional administrative authorities. Key concerns raised during the review included, ensuring beneficence and minimizing harm, maintaining patient confidentiality, and addressing data governance concerns due to WHO's role as the external developer. Each year, the centre seeks to renew its license for data collection from the data protection agency: *“We clearly stated in the protocol that the application does not collect data on the patient... The ethics committee is a reliable entity.”*

Theme 3: Benefit of digital health technology

The participant described several benefits resulting from the implementation and use of the WHO Skin NTD mobile application within clinical and surveillance activities. Although the number of confirmed cases of neglected tropical diseases (NTDs) detected was low, the application significantly improved awareness, case notification, diagnostic support, and engagement among health personnel. The application stimulated proactive reporting behavior among frontline workers, creating a ripple effect in diagnostic engagement: *“We follow up with the staff by WhatsApp and we have seen notifications of cases... Clearly, what we were looking for, we found very little, but we still found cases. That is important because we say that in terms of surveillance it is better to comb through the age rather than being rather specific, to avoid missing cases.”*

Another major benefit highlighted was the promotion of peer consultation and clinical decision-making support, particularly in remote or resource-limited settings: *“The main work that we did was not to remain silent when we have cases... It was to help us give your assessment of the case, help us make the diagnosis, but also help us provide care.”*

The participant also cited increased use of the application during fieldwork as a memory aid and reference tool: *"It means that at that time, someone was confronted with a case in the field, and the person looked in the application to see which case it could correspond to in the application."*

Furthermore, the application triggered a cultural shift towards early case identification and feedback loops among health professionals: *"We had a reaction for the search for cases... obviously we had awareness for the search for cases but also feedback to the expert, recourse to peers to have advice in terms of diagnosis of the case also of management."*

Additionally, the project team benefited from practical user feedback, which informed ongoing refinement of the app and associated training materials. Suggestions included improving image quality, adjusting video content, and providing multilingual options to enhance accessibility: *"Among the feedback, we have that it was necessary to improve the quality of the images in the application... For the application, it was to improve the colors, improve the photos, put the application in various languages."*

Theme 4: Stakeholder Engagement

The emphasis on stakeholder engagement was central to the implementation and integration of the WHO Skin NTD mobile application. Stakeholders were engaged at multiple levels of the health system, from national authorities to frontline health workers, ensuring institutional support and smooth dissemination of the digital health tool.

The process began with high-level engagement with the Ministry of Public Health, specifically the Disease Control Department and the sub-department in charge of NTDs. This early contact facilitated the project's alignment with national priorities and enabled the team to obtain ethical clearance and research authorizations: *"Even before reaching the level of health personnel, we started with the Ministry of Health... where we presented the project and had an agreement in principle for the execution of the project, which allowed us with the other elements of the file to submit for ethical clearance."*

From there, the team engaged regional delegations, securing research authorizations and coordinating with NTD focal points to ensure that the application reached the health districts and facilities: *“At the delegation level, the interaction was also with the NTD focal points... so that we could also reach the health centers and health personnel.”*

Stakeholder engagement continued at the district and facility levels, with efforts to train staff and raise awareness about the application’s purpose and functionality: *“We went to the health districts where we had authorization to go to the health facilities... At each level of the health pyramid, we had contacts, we presented... what the protocol was and the objectives of the research.”*

At the facility level, both individual and group engagement strategies were used to introduce and support health personnel: *“We have individual interviews where we meet a person, to whom we present the application... or it was a group interaction where we bring together health personnel, district heads... to present the application, its functionalities, how to use it, how to download it, etc.”*

Participant also highlighted the strategic use of existing networks and platforms, such as WhatsApp groups, to share information and maintain communication with stakeholders: *“We took advantage of their WhatsApp platform to pass on the information on the application so that the health personnel... also use the application in their training and in their case detection activity.”*

In addition to routine engagement, the team presented their work at national symposiums and training sessions to both disseminate the application and gather feedback: *“On September 20, 2024, we presented at the national symposium for research for NTDs... to present the application, to continue to disseminate, and to obtain feedback from other people... in relation to the methodology of evaluation and implementation.”*

Theme 5: Evaluation and Measurement

The participants provided insights into how the implementation of the WHO Skin NTD mobile application was evaluated, primarily focusing on reach, quality, and future potential impact assessment, in table below.

Sub-theme	Findings	Interview Excerpts
Indicators Used	The main indicator used was the number of app downloads, viewed as a proxy for initial reach and use.	<i>“Monitoring the download... was the first performance indicator.” “If no one has downloaded it, it’s clear that no one is going to use it.”</i>
Quality Assessment Tool	The quality of the app was assessed using the Mobile App Rating Scale (MARS), a standardized 18-item tool for evaluating mHealth applications	<i>“Downloads were assessed, but also an index of an average quality score of the application through the MARS tool.” “The tool allows us to give an average score for the application.”</i>
User Feedback	Informal evaluation was conducted through user feedback, leading to recommendations to improve image quality, video content, and languages.	<i>“Among the feedback, we have that it was necessary to improve the quality of the images... put the application in various languages.” “The feedback said the video was long or short... we used it to improve the videos.”</i>

Table IV: Sub-Themes on the Evaluation and Measurement of Digital Health Technology reported by participant at Institute of Science and Medical Research in Cameroon i.e. Mobile App Rating Scale

Theme 6: Challenges of Implementing Digital Health Technology

The challenges faced during the utilisation of these different tools are multifactorial. Many health personnel lacked access to mobile devices, reliable internet, or consistent electricity, which hindered adoption and use. These challenges are presented in the following interview excerpts: *“We cannot approach a person with mobile technology when the person does not have mobile tools... Access to electricity, to the internet — that is part of the challenges*

While the initial reception of digital health tools appears positive, the participant highlights significant infrastructural limitations, specifically limited access to electricity, internet connectivity, and basic mobile tools as barriers to effective implementation. This reflects a gap between user readiness and systemic capacity, suggesting that enthusiasm alone cannot ensure successful digital health adoption without addressing foundational access issues: *"Sometimes the requirements or complaints of the staff in the field were sometimes support in terms of internet, because you have to download the application, [Challenges] but it is true that, from the moment we downloaded it, we no longer needed internet. But to download it, the staff still asked if we could have support—megabytes to download it. And then, in terms of dissemination in the implementation part, they recommended that it would be better to do proper training, supported to present the application."* (Male, M&E Specialist, Cameroon). The excerpt above highlighted two key implementation challenges. First, internet access is a barrier even for tools that later function offline as health staff require mobile data to complete the setup process. Secondly, the need for comprehensive training during the rollout phase is critical. The recommendation for supported, structured training sessions reflects the importance of building capacity and ensuring confidence in using new digital tools.

Theme 7: Future Perspectives

The participant expressed plans to integrate **artificial intelligence (AI)** in future versions of the app to assist with diagnosis: *"A future version will integrate an artificial intelligence module... so that, those who have the application, from the moment they have taken a photo... the application tries to tell them which case it refers to.."*

By improving early and accurate diagnosis, DHT is expected to reduce incorrect treatments and antibiotic misuse: *"When the diagnosis has been poorly made... we will give bad treatment... which can lead to cases of resistance... it advances us in helping the patient."*

Furthermore, the participant sees mobile and digital technologies as transformative tools for improving patient outcomes and clinical decision-making: *"When we have these mobile and digital applications, which help us with decision-making or diagnosis, it advances us in helping the patient, and it advances us in the help we provide to the population."*

Case 3: Leveraging Digital Health Technologies to Advance Clinical Research in Socio-Political Conflict Zones: Case of the Centre for Research in Infectious Diseases (CRID, Cameroon)

Case description and use of technology

The Centre for Research in Infectious Diseases (CRID) in Cameroon enhances clinical research on neglected tropical diseases (NTDs) by leveraging digital health technologies. CRID focuses on vector-borne diseases such as malaria, as well as emerging diseases like Zika and dengue fever. By integrating these technologies, CRID improves data collection, real-time monitoring, and disease surveillance. This approach increases research efficiency and supports better health outcomes in the region. Collaborating with international partners, such as the Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine (LSTM), strengthens the utilization of digital tools and build local expertise.

Topic insights

Theme 1: Implementation of Digital Health Technology

The participant reported that, DHTs are been deployed within his organisation so as to enable data collection in hard-to-reach or conflict zones where traditional field methods were not feasible and reliable: *“It is difficult perhaps to reach all our target populations... especially in settings where there is conflict... So, we have to adopt digital technologies to collect data.”*

These tools are developed for community-based surveillance and data collection in real-time in conflict settings. *“We developed a digital tool to empower community health workers... they assess people and report through this SMS system.”*

The participant described a project were by digital health tools are been used to determine the effectiveness digital (SMS-based) and traditional (paper-based) systems in collecting data in clinical and community-based settings. The SMS based tool was used for malaria surveillance, disease mapping, and EPI follow-up. It enabled geolocation, symptom tracking, and referrals.

Theme 2: Ethical Issues

The implementation of digital health technologies was guided by strict adherence to ethical standards. Ethical approval was obtained from multiple levels, including the institutional review board, the national ethics committee, and the regional health authorities, ensuring the project met both local and national regulatory requirements: *“We just collected symptoms and possible signs... without including any personal identifiers... The SMS is stored in encrypted format... so even the telecom provider cannot read the content.”*

To maintain ethical standards during field activities, community health workers (CHWs) were trained not only in the technical use of the digital tools but also in core ethical practices such as informed consent, confidentiality, and respectful patient engagement: *“They were trained... on how to approach a participant... how to get consent, how to ensure that confidentiality is respected.”*

A custom-built encryption system was developed to secure all SMS-based data transmissions. This system ensured that only the Principal Investigator (PI) could decrypt and access the data, further reinforcing data privacy throughout the project lifecycle: *“Only my phone has the application to decrypt and send to the local server... We had to ensure that data confidentiality was respected even at the transmission level.”* These multi-layered ethical safeguards helped ensure that patient rights and data security were maintained across all phases of digital health technology implementation.

Theme 3: Benefits of implementing Digital health technology

Implementing DHT led to a host of benefits within the organization, the health system and the community. The participant stated several benefits such as improved access to crisis hit areas, real time data availability and a host of other benefits (Table V).

DHT: Digital Health Technology, CHW: Community Health Worker, EPI: Expanded Programme on Immunisation

Benefits	Findings	Interview Excerpts
Improved Access in Remote Areas	DHT enabled data collection in hard-to-reach or conflict-affected areas where fieldwork was not possible.	<i>“It is difficult perhaps to reach all our target populations... especially in conflict settings... So, we have to adopt digital technologies to collect data.”</i>
Real-Time Data availability	It enabled for immediate access to field data, enabling fast response to cases (e.g., severe malaria).	<i>“We receive it here in Yaoundé... and we could call them while they are still with the patient... and we were able to follow up the case.”</i>
Rapid Clinical Decision Support	Health teams intervened quickly in emergencies	<i>“We could immediately reach out to the field team and guide them on what to do based on the data received.”</i>
Community Surveillance	Strengthened community-based disease surveillance, allowing health workers to report and refer suspected cases directly from the field.	<i>“We trained CHWs to assess cases and report through SMS... they could detect and notify diseases like malaria, podoconiosis...”</i>

Multifunctionality	The tool could support multiple health programmes (e.g., malaria, disease mapping, EPI follow-up), making it a versatile digital solution.	<i>“We can use the same application for disease mapping... for EPI follow-up... and to collect malaria data in real-time.”</i>
Increased Health Worker Motivation	Health personnel and community workers felt empowered and appreciated, which improved morale and participation.	<i>“The community workers were very motivated because they were included in something new and impactful.”</i>
Data Accuracy and Integrity	Digital tools reduced errors associated with paper-based systems, improving data quality and timeliness.	<i>“We compared the digital and paper-based system... and the data from the digital method was more accurate and faster to access.”</i>

Table V: Benefits of implementing Digital health technology reported by participant at the Centre for Research in Infectious Diseases (CRID, Cameroon)

Theme 4: Stakeholder Engagement

Engagements with stakeholders was central to the successful implementation of DHT. These engagements occurred at various levels of the health system, beginning with collaboration with the Ministry of Public Health, regional delegations, and district medical officers. These partnerships were crucial for obtaining ethical clearances, selecting community health workers (CHWs), and ensuring institutional support for project activities: *“We collaborated with the health system... the Regional Delegation of Public Health, the health districts and the medical officers.”*

Stakeholders played a critical role in tool development and validation. Workshops were organized where national and regional health actors participated in pre-testing, ensuring that the digital system aligned with national health priorities and field realities: *“We organized workshops where stakeholders validated the tool... and ensured that it aligned with national malaria strategies.”*

At the operational level, health districts were responsible for selecting CHWs, strengthening local ownership. These CHWs were then trained in collaboration with regional health teams, creating a strong foundation of trust and engagement within communities: *“The health districts selected the CHWs... and we trained them in collaboration with local health authorities.”*

The projects also engaged local NGOs, academic researchers, and community-based organizations to support implementation, monitoring, and capacity building. These collaborations expanded the project's reach and enhanced technical support at the grassroots level: *"We worked with NGOs and researchers in the field to support training, supervision, and analysis."*

To maintain dynamic communication and technical support, WhatsApp groups were created with key stakeholders. These platforms were used to provide supervision, resolve field challenges, and gather continuous feedback on the tool's performance: *"We created a WhatsApp platform with the stakeholders... to receive feedback and provide support to the field workers."*

Finally, the success of the project sparked interest among regional health leaders in scaling up the tool for wider use, including possible adoption into national surveillance systems.: *"Many of the health officials said we should scale this tool to the whole region... and possibly use it in the national program."*

Theme 5: Evaluation and Measurement

The KI emphasized the importance of continuous evaluation and monitoring to ensure the effectiveness and improvement of the digital health tools. Multiple strategies were used to assess performance, user experience, and data quality. One of the key evaluation approaches was a comparative study between CHWs using digital tools (SMS-based) and those using traditional paper-based systems. This allowed the team to assess differences in data quality, response time, and overall feasibility: *"We had two groups: one using the SMS system and the other using the paper-based system because we wanted to compare the two."* The evaluation found that digital data collection was faster and more accurate, allowing for real-time review and response by the research and clinical teams: *"Once they sent the data, we received it here in Yaoundé and we could act immediately... It was a huge advantage compared to waiting for paper forms."*

Additionally, the evaluation included feedback from end users (CHWs and local health workers), who were able to report technical or operational challenges. This feedback informed continuous updates and training improvements: *"We had regular feedback sessions through WhatsApp and meetings... so we knew what was working and what needed to be improved."* Furthermore, system performance indicators such as number of cases detected, response time, data completeness, and CHW reporting rates were tracked over time to assess effectiveness and areas for optimization.

Theme 6: Challenges of Implementing Digital Health Technology

Several challenges were stated by the participant faced by the participant in implementing DHT. Some of these challenges centred around poor or unstable mobile network coverage in some regions made it difficult for CHWs to send SMS reports consistently: *“In some communities, they had to walk long distances just to find network... it delayed some reports.”*

Another key challenge was the lack of reliable electricity, which limited the ability of CHWs to keep their mobile phones charged. This was especially problematic in areas without access to generators or solar power, where maintaining consistent use of digital tools was difficult: *“Some CHWs complained that their phones would run out of battery and they had no power source to charge.”* Moreover, community health workers initially struggled to use the digital tools due to limited digital literacy: *“At first, some were afraid... they said they’ve never used a phone like this for such tasks.”*

Furthermore, resource constraints such as insufficient phones, power banks, and mobile airtime presented logistical difficulties. Not all CHWs could be fully equipped, and in many cases, personal phones were used for reporting: *“Some CHWs had no phones, or they used their own... we couldn’t provide for everyone.”*

The impact of socio-political instability, particularly "ghost towns" (days with enforced lockdowns or threats of violence) and security threats such as gunshots and roadblocks was a major hindrance to implementing this interventions. These conditions made it difficult for community health workers to conduct fieldwork or travel to submit data, especially in remote or conflict-prone areas: *“We always tell them to work maybe for 15 days... you find out maybe they will work for a month because of lockdowns... at times they cannot go out to work because they are gunshot.”* **Male, Public Health specialist, Cameroon)**

Theme 7: Future perspectives

A major future direction highlighted was the scaling and institutional integration of the digital tool beyond the pilot setting. Based on positive feedback from both health workers and authorities, the participant suggested that the tool could be adopted for use across multiple districts or integrated into national health surveillance systems: *“Many of the health officials said we should scale this tool to the whole region... and possibly use it in the national program.”*

Additionally, there was a strong interest in enhancing the **functionality and versatility** of the tool. Beyond malaria surveillance, the application is envisioned to support **routine immunization (EPI follow-up), disease mapping, and early warning systems** for epidemic-prone diseases: *“We can use the same application for disease mapping... to capture GPS coordinates and send real-time alerts. We also want to use it for EPI follow-up.”*

The participants also discussed **technical upgrades** for future versions of the system. These include improved user interfaces for health workers, increased offline capabilities, and possibly incorporating **decision-support algorithms** to assist CHWs in clinical judgment during fieldwork. There was a clear emphasis on sustainability through **local ownership** and **policy alignment**. Participant 8 envisioned deeper integration with the existing health information system and broader collaboration with **telecommunication providers, government agencies, and NGOs** to support dissemination and long-term maintenance: *“We hope to collaborate with more stakeholders so that this is not just a project tool... but something sustainable within the health system.”*

Finally, the participants expressed interest in expanding research to evaluate the long-term impact of digital tools on health outcomes, data quality, and disease surveillance efficiency. Such evidence could support advocacy for larger-scale digital transformation in health service delivery.

Case 4: Pregnancy Mobile App pilot clinical study – Kintampo Health Research Centre (KHRC) - Evaluation of electronic pregnancy registers and mobile applications as a potential tool for promoting antenatal care and monitoring pregnancy outcomes, Ghana

Description of use

This clinical study aims to evaluate the feasibility and acceptability of using open-source mobile applications in tracking pregnancy outcomes among pregnant women in sub-Saharan Africa.

Topic insights

Theme 1: Benefits of Implementing Digital Health Technology

The participant noted several benefits of implementing DHT within their organization. These were but not limited to enabling patients, especially pregnant women, to access care without visiting the facility: *“It will help the client, especially the pregnant women to save time and cost. Because they will not need to travel from their homes if it is not immediately.”* Also, the participant noted that implementing DHT reduces indirect costs for clients and reduces overhead costs for the health system. It decreased workload for workers, reducing the burden on midwives and other healthcare staff through remote communication. Moreover, data quality and direct reporting was made efficient due to this DHT. DHT, Enhanced quality and timeliness of data collection in clinical research: *“It will improve quality of data. Because for the digital technology, the person is giving her problem directly to you.”*

Theme 2: Security and confidentiality

Patients gave their consent before enrolling in the study.

Theme 3: Partnership and collaboration

There is collaboration between researchers. Scientific meetings are done every Monday and issues regarding any project are discussed there, researchers give their view and the work is improved.

Theme 4: Ethical evaluation

The protocol was reviewed by the Ghana Health Service Ethical Review, and the institutional ethics committee.

Theme 5: Challenges and Solutions

Participants have difficulties in keying in their information, because even though they are literate some of them who do not type well still make mistakes. One of the key technical features of the SMS application is its ability to function offline, allowing users to enter data without an active internet connection. However, the data could only be transmitted once a connection is available: *“The application was developed to work offline, so even if you don’t have internet connection, you can enter, but then it will require internet for the provider to receive the message.”* (Female, Data Manager, Ghana)

Despite this functionality, limited internet access emerged as a major challenge during implementation. Many users, particularly women attending antenatal care (ANC), either lacked smartphones or had devices without reliable internet connectivity: *“Most of the women coming for the ANC, some do not have smartphones, some smartphones without internet connection... those were some of the problems we encountered.”* (Female, Data Manager, Ghana)

These implementation hurdles prevent the adoption of DHT in clinical research among vulnerable populations in resource-limited settings. The effectiveness of digital tools depends not only on their design but also on the technological know-how of the end users.

Case 5: Using the UpScale digital health platform developed to support community health workers (CHWs) in Mozambique

Description of use

UpScale is a platform incorporated into the Android device, in this case the phone is used by the community and the staff which serves as an indicator to guide them and assist the populations or patients in their communities. The second aspect, the same application serves as a source of information and, thirdly, no less important, is that the device itself encompasses all the training modules for community health workers. It is a digital platform used by community health workers. It was a platform developed by the Malaria Consortium. At that time the Malaria Consortium decided to transfer the platform to the management of the APEs program. With the platform (UpScale) health workers make an improved diagnosis of patients and also help in the dosage of medicines for the same patients. For example, UpScale has a section where you enter the patient's age, weight, symptoms and signs of the disease and then the platform says that the patient has this disease and, based on the weight and age, it tells you what dosage of medication should be given to the patient. In the same UpScale, when the health agent does not know what the patients are suffering from, the platform tells them to refer the patient to the reference health unit.

Topic insights

Operational Plans

Depending on the type of problem the patient presents, there may be a patient with malaria and the device itself provides guidance on the dosage level of medication to be given to the patient and, if no medication is to be given, it recommends referring the patient to the health unit.

Theme 1: Functionality and features

The application has three essential functions, namely: 1) Helps in the diagnosis and dosage of the patient; 2) Indicates the need for the patient to be referred to the reference health unit and 3) Guidance guide for the APS (community health workers). Regarding the issue of guidance for the health agent, the platform has a training package for APS (community health workers) and they can consult the training manuals whenever they need it. The manuals are organized into modules that facilitate the recapitulation of the APS. The platform also helps to collect data on all health problems in the communities and this information on common illnesses and the number of cases is then used and integrated into the Health Information System (SISMA).

Theme 2: Operational Benefits

One of the advantages is also to pick up this device and work offline and when you have mobile data, you can send the information.

Another factor is that the information that is produced can be reported in real time for decision-making in the event of an outbreak of an epidemic, such as diarrhea.

It is easy for the supervisor or district coordinator, the monitoring and evaluation person to search for the information and discuss it for immediate decision-making.

All the training modules are incorporated into this application in digital format.

Also, using this platform to report information reduces the logbook, considering that the logbook is a little larger, you can use the application to later transfer it to the logbook.

Theme 3: Challenges and Solutions

One of the main challenges is the availability of mobile data that will allow it to report the information to the highest level.

Caring of the device: considering that the level of education of the APS (community health workers) themselves is low.

Lack of training: there is a need to have complete mastery, and most of these APs (community health workers) had never used a mobile or Android device before. The person in charge of the health unit must be monitoring how to use it, how to report information, and how to monitor a patient. The other factor is the allocation of monthly credit, which is often not financed by the National Health System, but by partners.

Lack of integrative infrastructure such as electricity

Theme 4: Security and confidentiality

All the information generated during consultations by health agents is reported in the monthly report and is stored directly in the cloud. Having the information in the cloud helps to collect consistent data, at low cost and very quickly. Therefore, in order for a person to have access to this information, individuals eligible for access must be registered in the system or platform. Anyone who is not registered does not have access to the information and we decided to have a few registered people. For example, in each province we have the provincial supervisors of the community health agents registered. These people must be registered so that they can have all the information and act on it. For example, if they find that a community health worker has low data, it is important to know what is going on. The data also helps with supervision. All data is kept confidential. In fact, when the community health worker collects information from patients, he or she does not usually give his or her name, and even in cases where he or she does give his or her name, we hide it when we intend to use the data.

Theme 5: Partnership and collaboration

UPSCALE has been able to secure funding from partners interested in maintaining the continuity of this application, from the Global Fund, the World Bank, UNICEF, USAID. So, it has been able to bring several investors to the country, allowing continuity and ensuring expansion. There is direct communication with the health unit supervisor, there is consistent communication between the APs (Community Health Workers), which can be from that district, that community, that province and the country in general, as long as they belong to that group of APs (Community Health Workers) because we assign them numbers to communicate and have access to the internet such as Save the Children,

Transformers Clinic, the Alcançar project, the Malaria Consortium, DMI with messages and videos, among others. The benefits of these partnerships are reciprocal, with the largest partners of the United Nations. The goal is to finance expansion, finance the use of the application, and we, as implementers, expand throughout the country, not in a limited way, but involving others.

Theme 6: Ethical oversight

Before conducting the study, a study protocol was submitted to the national bioethics commission, in which the researchers explained the entire process of implementing the study, expected results, use of data, protection of participants and all possible ethical issues that should be included in the study protocol. And during the pilot phase, scientists were very careful to ensure that everyone felt that they were being respected and that their rights were not being compromised. At that time, it was the first initiative in Mozambique and the ethical requirements were very high, there were fears about how we would use the data, whether health workers would be able to use the platform. In general, there was a lot of distrust and the way to reduce distrust was to be ethically rigorous and in the implementation of UpScale. Therefore, all the ethical protocols were observed and the team worked hard during the implementation to ensure that all these issues were respected

Theme 7: Future Perspectives

The UpScale app does not encompass all the components of the National Health System. Currently, with the introduction of the service..., there are some components that were introduced in the training package, such as oral health, some aspects related to HIV and some interventions that were already implemented, but that were not incorporated in the app, which was the distribution of herbs at the community level by the AP. The application will be upgraded to include the introduction of HIV, other aspects related to community nutrition.

Case 6: Using digital health technologies (DHTs) to enhance clinical research at the KAVI Institute of Clinical Research (KAVI-ICR), University of Nairobi, Kenya.

Description of use

The KAVI Institute of Clinical Research (KAVI-ICR) at the University of Nairobi is at the forefront of using digital health technologies (DHTs) to improve clinical research:

HIV Vaccine Trials: Digital platforms are employed for data collection, participant tracking, and real-time analysis, which helps manage HIV vaccine trials effectively.

Telemedicine: Remote consultations and follow-up appointments improve healthcare access for patients in remote areas.

Electronic Health Records (EHR): EHR systems streamline the management of patient data, reducing errors and enhancing the quality of care.

Mobile Health (mHealth) Applications: These applications help track health metrics, provide educational resources, and facilitate communication between patients and healthcare providers.

Remote Patient Monitoring: Devices monitor patients' health in real time, allowing for timely interventions in chronic conditions.

Data Analytics and AI: Advanced analytics and artificial intelligence (AI) are used to analyze large datasets, identify trends, and optimize research processes.

These initiatives demonstrate KAVI-ICR's commitment to advancing healthcare and clinical research in Kenya. Some interview quotes and verbatim transcriptions on the use of Digital Health Technologies (DHTs) for clinical research, along with discussions on ethical issues, impact assessment, data management, stakeholder engagement, future directions, and recommendations

Topics insights

Theme 1: Implementation and Integration of Digital Health Technologies

The participant, a male clinical trial researcher affiliated with the Faculty of Medicine at the University of Nairobi, offered rich insights into the current use and understanding of DHTs in clinical research within the institution. His perspective reflects the practical integration of DHTs into the research workflow, especially in the context of data collection and management. He identified several digital tools currently in use, including handheld devices such as tablets and mobile phones, which are employed for field data collection. According to the participant, these tools have become essential in gathering information directly and efficiently, reducing the reliance on traditional paper-based methods: *“We have hand phones and gadgets that you can use to collect data from study participants,”* he explained, highlighting the real-time and decentralized nature of these technologies.

One example provided was RADA, a mobile application developed and used within the university setting. This app is tailored for research purposes and its designed to meet specific project needs. The participant also mentioned the use of electronic data management systems, which support the integration of clinical data collected from health facilities into structured databases that are accessible for research and analysis: *“We have mobile apps that are used to conduct research... we have something called RADA, it's a mobile phone application.”*

The integration of these tools appears to be well-established in ongoing clinical trials, reflecting an institutional shift toward embracing technology in both operational and methodological aspects of research. While this integration enhances efficiency, it also reflects a broader shift in the research environment towards digitalization, especially in low-resource settings that are gradually adapting to technological advancement.

Theme 2: Ethical Issues in the Use of DHTs

The participant raised equity and confidentiality as major ethical concerns associated with using DHTs. In resource-limited settings, digital technologies may inadvertently exclude illiterate individuals from participating in research, thereby raising questions of justice and fairness in participant selection.

“...people who can be able to participate in studies... must be people who are literate... So, it raises the issue of equity.” He also highlighted the uncertainty about who accesses the data, especially once it's captured and uploaded, making confidentiality a critical ethical challenge: *“You are never very sure as to who is going to have access to that kind of data.”* Although their studies undergo review by a research ethics committee, no specific ethical impact assessments are conducted for the digital tools themselves. Current practices rely on traditional research ethics frameworks focusing on principles such as confidentiality, beneficence, and non-maleficence, without specific guidelines for emerging technologies like AI: *“We don't have specific AI guidance.”*

Theme 3: Data Security and Confidentiality

Concerns were also expressed about data storage and security. The participant emphasized the lack of control over data hosted on international servers, especially in multi-site, multi-country studies. The trust placed in researchers often depends on formal agreements, such as data transfer agreements, rather than tangible assurance of data protection: *“We completely rely on trust... we have no guarantee... The data is going to one site in a server where you have no access to it.”*

Theme 4: Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder engagement was noted as a gap in current practice when developing these applications. The participant acknowledged that no formal discussions have taken place between stakeholders such as drug

regulators, research ethics regulators, and researchers regarding the governance of DHTs. However, plans are underway to initiate such dialogue in the future: *“We have not really had a stakeholder discussion... this is something that is being planned.”*

Theme 5: Future Directions

Looking ahead, the participant called the integration DHTs in clinical research inevitability, and the need for capacity building among stakeholders, particularly research ethics committee members. He recommended training programs to equip both researchers and ethics committee members with the necessary knowledge to effectively evaluate and engage with digital technologies in research: *“We cannot run away from it... we just need to be more capacity built.....My recommendation is to train, train, train, members of research ethics committees on digital technology.”*

Case 7: A mobile app (educational video) designed to track and support adolescent sexual and reproductive health as well as adult mental health in South Africa

Operational Description

The meeting arrangements, followed by a site visit and discussions with three scientists in South Africa, were part of the 12th Annual Advancing Research Ethics Training in Southern Africa (ARESA) and the fourth Research for Ethical Data Science in Sub-Saharan Africa (REDSSA) seminars. These events allowed us to gather insights through semi-structured interviews. A key takeaway was the collaboration with Stellenbosch University on projects aimed at enhancing adolescent sexual and reproductive health, particularly the development of a mobile app for tracking health. The seminars also emphasized the use of digital health technologies, such as mental health apps and AI chatbots, to improve youth well-being in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs).

Topics insights

Theme 1: Benefits

Facilitates research through the speed and collation of data

Theme 2: Security and confidentiality

Difficulties in guaranteeing data protection or data privacy because there's always that small risks that could be breached.

Theme 3: Partnership and collaboration

Collaboration is done between people and organizations across Africa. This has led to more grants.

Theme 4: Ethical issues

Privacy and data protection; when that data is collected or stored, how secure is the storage?

Theme 5: Ethical guidelines

South Africa is regulated by POPIA, which is the Protection of Personal Information Act. Data protection is covered in this act, but it doesn't speak about research technologies. Nevertheless, a code of conduct is being developed, and that's the code of conduct for research. Global guidelines from WHO are still been used.

Theme 5: Stakeholder Engagement

There is an engagement with mostly the community, researcher and participants.

3.2. Use cases cross analysis

Using the coding book created, we conducted a thematic analysis by cross-referencing various use cases and identifying categories or themes. The results are presented below.

Theme 1: Identification and roles of digital health technologies (DHTs)

Online platforms/DHTs are used in the following ways:

- a. To collect data (ODK, Python, Power BI, YACO for Vaccination, hand phones, RADA)
- b. For clinical trials. For example, in the context of a clinical study on podoconiosis (a neglected tropical disease requiring accurate clinical diagnosis)
- c. DHTs are also used in areas with existing conflict like Northwest region of Cameroon to recruit participant from clinical trials using SMS tools.
- d. In randomisation for clinical trials (REDCAP)
- e. To communicate and educate people using videos in order to create awareness on sexual and reproductive health as well as adult mental health.
- f. To Package data (DHIS2, ONA)

- g. For data Analysis (EXCEL and ERP, YACO, AGIS)
- h. For micro-planning
- i. For Diagnosis (Skin Entities, artificial intelligence). The Oascope is a kind of miniaturized microscope also base on artificial intelligence train to detect the movements of microfilariae in the blood, count it and make the diagnosis.
- j. For treatment purposes especially among younger people. The population mostly use DHTs to better understand their health. They mostly use apps concerned with reproduction, sexual health and mental health.
- k. To track menstrual cycle

Theme 2: Benefits of DHT

Several benefits of DHTs were reported by some participants. These benefits include:

a. Accessibility of real-time data collection:

- Digital health technology helps **collect** and **bring all data together** so that healthcare professionals or researchers can have a bigger picture.
- It makes health services more accessible, especially in **hard-to-reach areas** or during **times of crisis**.
- It helps to collect data on all health problems in the communities integrated into Health Information System (SISMA).

b. Improving Decision Making and Diagnosis:

- Digital tools allow healthcare professionals to use **apps as diagnostic aids**,
- Health care decisions are fast.
- Improved **case reporting** and **real-time** disease surveillance, particularly during epidemics such as cholera.

c. Flexibility and Increased Monitoring:

- DHT, helps to speed up decision-making in case of epidemic disease or diagnosis, enhancing cross referencing among disease centers data basis to better mitigate the spread of contagious diseases.
- These tools help in **rapid data collection** and real-time adaptation of strategies, which is essential for **flexible and responsive management** of health situations, particularly in emergency situations.

d. Efficiency and cost reduction

- **Digital technologies** centralize **data**, providing a comprehensive overview of research and health efforts.
- This improves the **speed**, **accuracy**, and **efficiency** of data collection, organization, and analysis processes thereby reducing finances associated with data collection, participant tracking, and human error management.
- e. **The digitalization of information**
 - The digital health technology reduces the use of registry books, which are frequent and have limitations in the reliability of the data.

Theme 3: Operational Challenges

a. Availability and quality of the tools

- The tools used in DHTs are quite expensive and there is a lack of expertise.
- The permanent need of quality control and assistant of the tools.
- There is also a challenge on the scientific validity of the tools.

b. Storage of Data

- There is a problem in the renting of the server and storage of the mega data
- Lack of basic infrastructures especially in low income/rural communities

c. Practical challenges

- The access to electricity and internet is limited and there is a deficit of mobile tools
- There is a need for training of the staff in the field.
- There is interoperability and governance
- Sustainability of the tools
- Some of the tools are not user-friendly and require fine-tuning and upgrade in relation to real life needs.

Theme 4: Partners and Collaboration

Partnerships and inter-institutional collaboration are essential for the success of digital health technology projects, enabling improved research, implementation and dissemination of these technologies at local,

national and international levels. These collaborations include partnerships with international institutions, local organizations and government actors, helping to strengthen the quality, sustainability and impact of health technologies.

a. International Partnerships and Collaboration with Global Institutions

- Researchers collaborate with institutions in Africa, Europe, and the United States, enriching research with diverse perspectives. Long-term partnerships are often formed.
- Collaborations with international organizations such as the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, the Clinton Foundation, and the WHO are strengthening the infrastructure of digital health systems, particularly for vaccination campaigns and neglected tropical disease (NTD) programmes have been successful in developing and efficiently using digital health technologies such as Oascope and other decision support tools for skin diseases.
- WHO played a crucial role in the development of SkinApps, a decision support tool for skin diseases, collaborating with Cameroon for its implementation. Collaboration with international universities has led to the development of tools such as those for scabies detection, which contributes to innovation in public health.

b. National Partnerships and Local Collaborations

- At the national level, partnerships with institutions such as the University of Yaoundé 1 and the National Advanced School of Engineering support the development of health technologies, particularly in the areas of artificial intelligence and health data management. Collaborations with researchers enable the development of digital solutions adapted to the specific health challenges in the region.
- Partnerships with the Ministry of Health and regional delegates ensure successful implementation and wide dissemination of technologies. For example, collaboration with NTD focal points strengthened case detection and improved disease control campaigns. Local NGOs facilitated the dissemination of the app to field workers, which strengthened the app's impact on the ground, ensuring the quality and continuity of services. Collaboration with local communities and data managers is crucial to ensure the integrity and reliability of data collected in the field.
- The involvement of community health workers is continually assessed to better understand how to enhance their effectiveness via the platform and adjust the available tools. This collaboration with Eduardo Mondlane University, particularly the Faculty of Medicine, facilitates data analysis and the identification of areas that require improvement.

c. Challenges and Opportunities of Collaboration

- Logistical and administrative challenges: Although these partnerships enrich research and technology implementation, they also generate logistical and administrative challenges, particularly regarding financing, data transfer agreements, and security regulations.
- Strengthening collaboration with stakeholders: Currently, there is a need for deeper stakeholder involvement in discussions on the impacts of new digital technologies in research. Such collaborations are important to optimize the integration of technologies and ensure their long-term effectiveness.
- Participation and co-construction with communities: co-construction with Communities are a key factor in ensuring acceptance and integration of digital health technologies, including training users and providing on-the-ground support.
- Reciprocal Benefits: partnerships enable the platform to scale quickly while ensuring a positive impact on public health through the integration of prevention messages and community engagement.
- Financial and Resource Partnerships: major partners such as WHO and UNICEF finance the platform's associated costs, enabling the infrastructure to be maintained, while other partners (e.g. Save the Children) provide educational content to enrich the platform.

Theme 5: Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder engagement proves to be a necessity and is influenced by several parameters related to the study's topology and the level at which one is positioned in the study. In general, several collaborations are to be noted. It is also an ethical obligation for researchers to continuously engage with stakeholders in the community. This shows the necessity of communication among stakeholders:

- a. Collaboration between researchers and service providers (communication to reduce gaps and create more contact: creating more partnerships and research institutes).
- b. Community or research participants (emphasizes the importance of piloting) with researchers. This could be done by creating an open communication with participants and reducing the risks of participations.
- c. Institution and government; this could be done by building more infrastructures and research institutes.

Theme 6: Ethical Issues

The ethical question for most participants focuses on ensuring the confidentiality of data, the anonymity of participants, reducing the impact, the benefit-risk ratio: the ethics of equity, in matters of consent. Some participants reported that there might be some breaches or flaws since the servers in which data are stored, even if they are encoded, are not local servers. Confidentiality is therefore one of the aspects to be taken into account ethically. Participants also reported issues of equity and data sharing agreements, which are indeed disadvantageous to DHT. There is a concern about the social consequences of data leaks, particularly how misinterpreted health information (e.g., a "positive" test result) could lead to stigma and negative social repercussions for participants. Researchers and health workers must be aware of the potential stigma caused by misinterpretations of health data and ensure confidentiality to protect participants from social harm.

From the analysis, most of the ethical considerations centered around 1). confidentiality is not one hundred percent guaranteed. 2). equity and data sharing practices are not favorable with DHT, and 3). The possible misinterpretations of health data. In terms of **recommendations to mitigate such issues, there is the need to train** researchers and ethics committees members on how to manage projects involving digital technologies.

Theme 7: DHT Regulation

Participants reported existing regulation and ethical guidelines related to digital health technologies but no specific AI guidance. The suggestion was that the content of the technology guide that has been digitized into mobile application came from global agencies such as the WHO and hence its validity.

- a. Existing regulations and ethical guidelines such as POPIA (Protection of Personal Information Act) in South Africa, which is the Protection of Personal Information Act,
- b. WHO GCP guidelines for the ethical and effective use of DHTs, including mobile health (mHealth) applications, telehealth, and electronic health records. They emphasize the importance of integrating DHTs into health systems and ensuring they meet safety, efficacy, and quality standards. These regulations, though present, are not fairly respected by researchers due to lack of knowledge of its existence and lack of digitalization.

Theme 8: Perspectives and Future Development of Partnerships

Relating to the perspectives of these technologies, participants reported the need for:

- a. **Capacity Building and Training**

- Capacity building is crucial to train healthcare teams, researchers, and ethics committees in the use of digital technologies. Tailored training programs will enable users to maximize the effectiveness of the tools.
- It is necessary to Train researchers and ethics committees on how to manage projects involving digital technologies, particularly in the context of clinical research and impact assessments, where unconventional data (from populations outside traditional clinical environments) will be increasingly used.

b. Financing Support for Implementation

- Funding is crucial to expand the use of technologies, particularly to ensure sustainability and for tools to reach the areas where they are most needed. Financial support will also help address infrastructure and accessibility issues.
- Future collaboration with platforms such as MTN could enable increased dissemination of the application, particularly during one-off campaigns, to assess its effectiveness and improve its impact on the ground. Continued collaborations with international and national partners are needed to pilot and adjust digital health tools to local needs, while increasing the reach of disease control programs.
- Financial and technical partnerships with organizations such as The World Bank, WHO, The Global Fund, UNICEF and GIZ does not only support the implementation of technologies, but also train users and conduct surveys to improve understanding of health challenges in different contexts. Save the Children, Malaria Consortium, disseminate prevention messages, particularly for malaria, and contribute content; and DMI (Development Media International) is a partner specialized in creating multimedia content (videos, messages) for the dissemination of public health messages.

c. Adoption of AI to digital health technology

- Digital and emerging technologies will gradually become more common in research and patient health management. This will facilitate disease detection and diagnosis and improve the quality of care through automation. While the adoption of AI and digital technologies carries **potential risks** (data security issues, algorithmic bias, etc.), as the technology matures, these risks will become more manageable, and appropriate solutions will be implemented to mitigate them.
- Installing the tool in a laptop or desktop device with the possible to use it offline, even if there is no internet.

d. Government and intercontinental support

- Participants emphasized the importance of government support for rapid digital architecture in healthcare institutions. This includes establishing solid foundations for data collection and coordination among sector stakeholders.
 - The development of local infrastructure, such as a national server for data storage, would facilitate data management without relying on external servers. Regulations on personal data security, such as the recent presidential decree in Cameroon, are necessary to ensure the confidentiality of sensitive information.
 - The goal of platform expansion is to broaden the use of the platform across the country by involving more actors (community health workers, medical institutions, etc.) to spread key public health messages. Integrate new modules into the platform, strengthen the dissemination of key messages through partners, and expand the initiative's reach to other regions of the country. Platform expansion should not be limited within national boundaries but across the continent giving centers for disease control the opportunity to cross-reference symptoms to better mitigate the spread of contagious and better manage the outbreak of epidemics. Such cross referencing enhances knowledge sharing and cross referencing in complex diagnostic situations. Investing in new technologies, AI tools and the training of personnel equally benefits platform expansion.
 - Respect for WHO ethical protocols via the inter-country data sharing protocols among centers for disease control must subscribe to WHO ethical evaluation protocols to avoid data leaks and the violation of patient confidentiality.
- e. Possible future research projects include the evaluation of DHT infrastructure to enhance tele-medicine and remote consultations especially in conflict areas and difficult to access rural locations. Also the possibility of unifying DHTs infrastructures to increase functionality and easy data and knowledge sharing with the continent.

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

Summary of key Issues and Challenges:

- a. Most research centers lack an Institutional Review Board (IRB) or an ethics committee, which means all research protocols must be reviewed by the National Ethics Committee.
- b. Researchers have raised concerns about the quality of ethical review reports, often finding them unsatisfactory or not aligned with their project's scope. Furthermore, some members of research

ethics committees may not be fully equipped to review projects involving Digital Health Technologies (DHTs).

- c. It is difficult to find use cases that describe clinical trial projects exclusively, as these often combine research with healthcare practices.
- d. Most projects have not conducted ethical impact assessments regarding the DHT tools used.
- e. Nearly all projects or centres do not own their data servers, raising issues surrounding data security and ownership.
- f. Contacting key informants and stakeholders, as well as conducting remote interviews via Zoom or Teams calls, has proven challenging across different countries.
- g. Internet connectivity poses significant challenges in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), as platforms like Teams and Zoom require substantial bandwidth.
- h. Frequent electricity outages in Sub-Saharan Africa highlight the need for renewable or green energy solutions.

Best Practices:

- a. Protocols for all projects and use cases were developed and reviewed by the relevant ethics committee before implementation.
- b. Collaborative partnerships among scientists were noticed, particularly for funded projects, including those supported by the EU-EDCTP, NIH, Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation, WHO/TDR, Wellcome Trust, UNICEF, and GIZ.
- c. Research centres are organizing open days for researchers to showcase their findings.
- d. Scientists are actively seeking both in-person and online training opportunities from the STRATEGIC Consortium.

Opportunities:

- a. Networking can facilitate the recruitment of stakeholders for future exchanges.
- b. There is potential to create a sustainable online community for discussing critical issues through focus group discussions, stakeholder consultations, policy roundtables, and consensus workshops.
- c. Collaborative partnerships can be developed for future grant applications and technology transfer initiatives.

Recommendations:

- a. It is essential to establish research ethics committees in clinical research centers throughout Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA).
- b. Existing research ethics committees in SSA clinical research centers should be strengthened, along with the National Ethics Committees.
- c. Enhancements to data management systems in Africa are necessary, addressing issues related to data server ownership.
- d. Partnerships with the WHO should be pursued to implement sustainable online training programs, such as TRREE and Good Clinical Practice (GCP) online training.
- e. Solutions must be found to address internet connectivity challenges

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Appendixes

Appendix 1: Criteria for Identification of Use Cases of Digital Health Technologies for Clinical Trials and research

It is important to note that the focus of STRATEGIC is on digital health technologies used for clinical trials and research. These are technologies used at any stage of clinical trial or research. These technologies play a crucial role in modernising clinical trials and research by improving efficiency, accuracy, and patient engagement. Here are some of the key digital health technologies used in this domain:

1. Electronic Data Capture (EDC) Systems

- **Usage:** EDC systems collect and manage clinical trial data electronically.
- **Applications:** Streamlining data collection, reducing errors, and facilitating real-time data access and analysis.

2. Electronic Case Report Forms (eCRFs)

- **Usage:** eCRFs are digital versions of paper case report forms used in clinical trials.
- **Applications:** Capturing and storing patient data more efficiently, ensuring data consistency, and improving data quality.

3. eConsent Platforms

- **Usage:** eConsent platforms allow participants to provide informed consent electronically.
- **Applications:** Enhancing the consent process, improving participant understanding, and enabling remote consent.

4. Electronic Patient-Reported Outcomes (ePRO)

- **Usage:** ePRO systems collect data directly from patients about their health condition and treatment via electronic means.
- **Applications:** Capturing real-time patient feedback, improving patient engagement, and collecting data for endpoints in clinical trials.

5. Wearable Devices and Biosensors

- **Usage:** Wearable devices collect continuous health data from participants.
- **Applications:** Monitoring vital signs, tracking physical activity, detecting adverse events, and collecting objective data for clinical trials.

6. Remote Monitoring and Telemedicine

- **Usage:** Remote monitoring technologies and telemedicine facilitate patient monitoring and interactions without in-person visits.
- **Applications:** Conducting remote site visits, ensuring patient adherence, and managing patient safety.

7. Clinical Trial Management Systems (CTMS)

- **Usage:** CTMS are software solutions that manage the planning, tracking, and reporting of clinical trials.
- **Applications:** Streamlining trial management, tracking trial progress, and ensuring regulatory compliance.

8. Electronic Health Records (EHRs) Integration

- **Usage:** Integration with EHRs allows clinical trial data to be linked with routine clinical data.

- **Applications:** Facilitating patient recruitment, accessing real-world data, and supporting post-market surveillance studies.

9. Big Data and Advanced Analytics

- **Usage:** Leveraging large datasets and advanced analytics to inform clinical research.
- **Applications:** Identifying patient populations, optimizing trial design, and analyzing trial data for insights.

10. Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML)

- **Usage:** AI and ML algorithms analyse complex datasets to identify patterns and make predictions.
- **Applications:** Predicting patient outcomes, optimizing patient recruitment, and identifying biomarkers.

11. Natural Language Processing (NLP)

- **Usage:** NLP processes unstructured text data from various sources.
- **Applications:** Extracting relevant information from clinical notes, automating data extraction, and identifying patient eligibility.

13. Mobile Health (mHealth) Applications

- **Usage:** mHealth apps are used to engage participants and collect data via mobile devices.
- **Applications:** Enabling patient recruitment, facilitating real-time data collection, and improving patient adherence.

14. Virtual Trials (Decentralised Trials)

- **Usage:** Virtual trials leverage digital technologies to conduct clinical trials remotely.
- **Applications:** Reducing the need for physical site visits, increasing patient diversity, and improving trial accessibility.

This list represents only examples and is in no way exhaustive.

Appendix 2: Use Cases Analysis Interview Guide

This guide contains questions designed to gather information from investigators and program managers regarding the impact and opportunities of digital health technologies in clinical research in Sub-Saharan Africa.

General Understanding

- 1- What digital health technologies are currently used in your organisation?
- 2- Describe your role related to digital health technologies in clinical research.

Implementation and Integration

- 3- What do you use the digital technology to do as regards of clinical research/trial? What challenges have you encountered when implementing these technologies?
- 4- How do you integrate them into existing clinical workflows?

Ethical issues

- 5- What ethical issues do you think this digital technology raises in clinical research and trial?
- 6- Did you conduct any ethical impact assessment, ethics reviews before the use of the technologies?
- 7- What available regulations or ethical guidelines are you adhering to in the use of these technologies? Any relevant ethical or regulatory body related to your work?

Benefits and Impact

- 8- What benefits have you observed using digital health technologies?
- 9- Can you share examples of improved patient outcomes or research efficiency?

Data Management and Security

- 10- How do you ensure the security and confidentiality of patient data? Which measures are in line with regulatory requirements for data management?

Stakeholder engagement

- 11- How do you involve patients and stakeholders (e.g. researchers, ethics committee, national regulatory authority) in the deployment of these technologies? What feedback have you received?

Future directions

- 12- What trends do you foresee in digital health technologies for clinical research? What innovations would you like to see?

Evaluation and measurement

- 13- How do you measure the success of these technologies and what key performance indicators (KPIs) do you

use?

Collaboration and partnerships

14- How do you collaborate with other organisations in the field of digital health

15- What partnerships have been most beneficial for your initiatives?